

Jirgas and the Ways Political Decisions Were Shaped in the Modern History of Afghanistan (1709–1922)

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Abstract: This article examines the role of Jirgas as one of the most important and influential authorities in political decision-making in the modern history of Afghanistan, between 1709 and 1922. The aim of this research is to examine and analyze how major socio-political decisions were managed by Jirgas during this period in Afghan history. The research method in this article is qualitative in nature, with a historical-analytical approach, citing reliable historical sources, classical methods, social crisis management, political power transfer, and finally, state-building through popular meetings and traditional Jirgas, in which Jirgas have been a reliable decision-making and determining authority in these developments. The research findings clearly show that in societies that still had a tribal system and feudal order, where there were no written laws, ethnic jirgas, as a respected authority among the majority of the people, had the greatest effectiveness and efficiency in social interactions and political developments. In terms of how the Jirgas were formed, their role, and effectiveness,

the research results show that these Jirgas had different methods and functions at different times and even in different geographies of Afghanistan, depending on the power structure, social values, conditions, and culture of the time. The results of the research show that ethnically influential people, clerics, and large feudal lords, who had extensive popular and economic influence, were considered among the most important factors and elements that played a fundamental and prominent role in legitimizing, strengthening, weakening, and even dismissing the kings and shaping the political developments of the country, because historical evidence shows that systems that relied on the military and were absolute had a shorter lifespan than systems that were supported by the people under the leadership of these Jirgas. Therefore, Jirgas have always played the role of supporting or opposing regimes and acting as a link or severing authority between the state and the nation.

Keywords: *Jirgas, political decision-making, Modern history, transfer of power, political legitimacy, traditional and customary systems*

Introduction

Jirgas, as an important credible popular authority and one of the most historical traditional and customary institutions, have played an effective and decisive role in the socio-political developments of Afghanistan. This traditional and ancient authority, which was formed on the

basis of consensus, consultation, and the participation of elders and influential people in society, has not only acted to resolve popular conflicts and ethnic differences, but has also acted as one of the most important channels for shaping systems and as a reference for major political decisions at different historical stages. In this regard, a careful study of Jirgas throughout history is of particular importance for a proper understanding of the ways in which political power rises and falls, legitimizes and delegitimizes political systems, and directs socio-political movements.

In modern Afghan history, especially from the early 18th century onwards, Jirgas emerged as a powerful and robust force in the country's political arena and played a central role in major national decision-making. The selection of political leaders, the appointment of kings, the legitimization of political systems, the management of the country's political conflicts, and the ratification of national documents and laws were among the issues that were approved or rejected through these Jirgas at different points in history. The above cases indicate that in modern Afghanistan, decisions were not only based on the decisions of official institutions but also on the collaboration of popular-social interactions through Jirgas. In some cases, Jirgas have been used as a source of legitimacy for kings' decisions, sometimes as a tool to maintain balance between parties claiming the throne, and sometimes as a source of power to maintain dominance and the continuity of power, which depends on the expertise and ability of the rulers.

Most of the research that has been conducted on Jirgas in Afghanistan has been descriptive in nature, rather than focusing on the processes by which these Jirgas influence political decision-making in Afghanistan. Therefore, there was a fundamental need to conduct research on this subject and analyze the issues from this perspective.

Considering all this, how these Jirgas were formed, the methods of launching this great national consensus, and how it was used, especially between the years 1709 and 1922, require in-depth and evidence-based research.

This research, focusing on the historical period between the years 1709 and 1922, attempts to examine Jirgas not only as part of the events of the country's history, but also as authorities for shaping political affairs and major historical decisions affecting the fate of the country.

Research Method

This research is a qualitative study with a historical-analytical approach in, which uses this method to examine the role of Jirgas in shaping political decisions in the modern history of Afghanistan between 1709 and 1922. In terms of data collection, this research has used the library and documentary study method, and efforts have been made to rely on reliable domestic and foreign sources and foreign sources in this research. The analysis of information in this research is based on interpretive historical analysis. Instead of simply describing events, an attempt has been made to analyze the decisions taken in these assemblies in relation to the historical and political contexts of each period.

Background

Throughout its history, which is full of epic struggles, the people of Afghanistan have always sought to create a conducive environment for the formation of social organizations in order to regulate social and political life on important issues and thus utilize the views and opinions of the majority in society. It is important to note that these communities have traditionally existed in the social life of our people as a phenomenon with social value in regulating social affairs. For this reason, the existence of local assemblies has not only formed the core of social organization at the local level but, according to the necessities of different periods, has often played a major historical role in resolving important issues of national life.

The idea of creating such social organizations (Jirgas) originated from the heroic liberation struggles of our fathers and ancestors against colonialism and imperialism and for the freedom and independence of Afghanistan. In the light of such Jirgas, the people of our country have given and continue to give a crushing response to the enemies of our homeland throughout the history of their political struggles. This historical assembly, through which solutions to the political and social problems of our society have always been sought and continue to be sought, is called the Loya Jirga (Great Consultative Assembly), which represents the direct will of the people of our homeland. The Loya Jirga of Afghanistan, which exists in other countries in the form of a Constituent Assembly, has existed in our country for centuries and serves as a direct representative of the people's participation in society.

In various historical sources of Afghanistan, there have been discussions about Jirgas and the historical course of these historic. For example, Mr. Mehrban (1989), in his work entitled History of National Jirgas, has discussed the historical course of Jirgas in the history of Afghanistan. In his book Afghanistan in the Path of History, Ghabar (1989) mentions the role of Jirgas and their historical course as a traditional and important institution in Afghan society. Similarly, Shahristani (2007) discusses the historical course of Jirga in Afghanistan and the role of the emergency Loya Jirga. Binwa (1958), in his work entitled Hotakis, has discussed the Jirgas of the Hotaki period. In general, various historical books of Afghanistan have frequently addressed discussions about the historical development of these Jirgas. What this research seeks to examine is the role of the Jirga in the process of shaping Afghanistan's political decisions within the historical context.

When we study the history of Jirgas in the pages of Afghan history, we see that the people of this land have had assemblies such as Jirgas for centuries, through which members of society have, in one way or another, participated in major socio-political decisions. A clear example of this can be found in the lines of the country's ancient history; in ancient Aryana, there were two assemblies called Subha (common people) and Simathy (nobles), which were not only the core of social organization at the local level, but also, according to the necessities of the time, played a valuable and historical role in solving important issues of national life (10:125)

These Jirgas and national assemblies became the main elements in the development and manifestation of political and social life in the ancient Afghan society, and this valuable tradition still holds a respected position in the political and national life of our society today. Because Jirga is an important meeting in Afghan society that is formed to implement ethnic consultations, its decision assumes the status of law. Afghans have had laws since ancient times to regulate their social life, and these laws have been established from time to time by the Jirgas (5:286).

Our article is chronologically focused on the contemporary period of Afghanistan; therefore, we will not discuss the ancient Jirgas of Afghanistan (Ariana and Khorasan) further. Our main focus is on the Jirgas from 1709 to 1922, which are discussed in detail in this article.

The meaning of the word Jirgas in Afghanistan

The word Jirga in Persian means to circle, to describe the gathering of people (argument), to line up a crowd, and to form a circle. The word jirga in Arabic is the equivalent of the word "council" (Chora) and is called (Conseil) in French (7:375). The word "council" means to inquire and consult. Mr. Abdullah Mehraban considered it a Turkish word (12:459).

It has been used in the literature of the country's history as a synonym for "Shura" and has achieved a special and strong social position among different tribes. According to authoritative books and the opinions of scholars and scientists, the word "Jarga", the plural of which is "Jirgi",

in Pashto refers to a council that has the authority to make decisions and whose ruling is accepted. In general, a Jirga is any type of meeting that aims to resolve tribal issues, especially those meetings where tribal elders or clans gather to resolve ethnic problems and issues, eliminate discord and establish unity between people and tribes. Similarly, anyone who does not accept the decision of the Jirga or defies it is subject to severe punishment in Afghan society (3:1272).

Considering history, the evolution of Jirgas during different periods from ancient times to the present day, has been full of complex events. In our country, the struggle of progressive forces against the oppressive relations of internal powers, exploitation and foreign colonialism has been reflected by Jirgas. The tradition and practice of Jirgas and Shura in our land have a historical precedent, and our ancestors have made good use of this desirable and valuable tradition throughout history, especially after the advent of Islam. In the past, with the development of social life in Ariana and ancient Khorasan and the establishment of a political system to ensure public interests, the need to form national forces and Jirgas was felt. For this reason, local Jirgas have played a valuable and historical role in solving important national issues according to the needs of the time. Jirgas have become major elements in the development and manifestation of political and social life in society. This tradition has held a high position in the political and national life of our society from ancient times to the present day. Jirga, which embodies expediency, consultation and wisdom, is an important meeting in our society formed to implement ethnic and governmental consultations, through which social and political issues of the society are resolved, and its decisions assume the status of law among the people. It should be noted that most of the laws of society throughout history have been enacted by these Jirgas, which have played and continue to play a major and effective role in regulating social life, and all members of society have valued and supported them. Jirgas have strengthened the spirit of unity among individuals and have influenced the fate of all ethnic groups and communities through social life and their environment. The more problems members of society face, the more seriously they have strived to defend the Jirgas.

Jirgas have strengthened the efforts and activities of the community in ensuring unity and, with their special features, have played an effective role in regulating the life of the community and resolving all problems. To some extent, they have held the prestige of a legislative branch, through which the elders of the tribes have resolved internal and external issues throughout history. National Jirgas have never been under the influence of influential people, and their members have participated in resolving national issues. The importance of the decisions of the Jirgas is that no one can ignore or deny them. Jirgas play a crucial role in preventing war and revenge, resolving people's conflicts, and ensuring peace and security. typically, judicial matters, family issues, and similar disputes are better resolved through Jirgas, which have determined and established specific penalties (14:45).

Jirgas have always issued their decisions and rulings in accordance with established national traditions. They have been a characteristic institution all ethnic groups and nationalities, including Pashtuns, Tajiks, Hazaras, Uzbeks, Turkmens, Balochs, Nuristanis, Sadats, and other nationalities, and have existed in various forms.

Jirgas and the Ways Political Decisions Were Shaped in the Modern History of Afghanistan

Jirgas have played a fundamental role in the formation of political decisions throughout the history of Afghanistan, and whenever the people of Afghanistan have faced challenges, especially in major national issues, they have turned to Jirgas.

The Loya Jirga of 1709 and the Formation of the Hotakian Government

The Jirga convened in 1709 by Mirwais Khan Hotaki had national and social values and was able to play an effective role in the social and political life of our society. After the fall of the Timur's government in Herat and the disintegration of national unity, the ground was prepared for the invasion of the Safavids of Iran into the territory of Afghanistan. The Safavid government of Iran, by using the method of division and religious fanaticism, consolidated its power daily until the "wolf", the political representative of that government, took out the hand of oppression from his sleeve and made the social and political environment even more constricted for the working people. He committed boundless and endless acts of oppression, and since life under captivity for Afghans is like dying in humiliation, patriotic people sought to eliminate the "wolf" and turned to the formation of ethnic and national jirgas, drawing on the ancient and valuable traditions of Afghan people (13:54).

Accordingly, the first national Jirga in the history of the eighteenth century of Afghanistan was drawn up, and the first meeting of this great national Jirga was held in 1709 in the village of Kokran, located in the west of Kandahar city. They showed their strong support for Mirwais Hotaki's opposition to giving his daughter to a foreigner, a long-time enemy of Afghans.

The second session of the National Jirga was held on this issue, and all the elders and respected men, according to the traditions of Afghan society, swore an oath of loyalty to the Quran, sword, bread, and salt, which are respected by them, and expressed their cooperation with Mirwais Khan, encouraging him to strengthen national unity and rise against the enemy. They also emphasized that, in order to deceive and gain the trust of the Wolf, he should send one of his servants to his house to marry the Wolf's son in order to save the country from the clutches of foreigners.

The third session of this great national and historical Jirga, in which the most important national and historical guarantee of the country's freedom from the clutches of foreigners was arranged, was held secretly a month later in (Manjeh), thirty miles northeast of Kandahar, near the city of Safa. A definitive decision was made that the "wolves" and the Iranian army should be exterminated together and a free national government should be established. In this Jirga, the duties of the leaders and their affiliated tribes were determined so that they would be prepared to preserve freedom and confront any military incident of the Safavid's government (8:319).

The persistent efforts, ability, and initiative of Mirwais Khan led this Jirga to happily accept his leadership at the head of the national forces. The outstanding feature of this Jirga was that, unlike the previous ones, the chiefs of the Abdali and Ghilja tribes, Tajik, Hazara, Uzbek and Baloch tribes, including influential mullahs, were organized as a single national force, and the regulations of the Jirga were implemented with complete calm and secrecy. This secrecy was so skillfully done that not a single person from the government's masters felt the slightest sensation until the appointed hour, while the insurgent forces were being mobilized on every side.

One of the rules of the Jirga was that, since there were a large number of Iranian and Georgian troops inside the fortified city, they had to be provided with the means to leave. Eventually, the Baluch and Kakari chiefs did not pay taxes, and Gargin left the city to suppress them. At a gathering one night in Arghistan, in a garden at midnight, Mirwais Khan and his vengeful men stabbed them with swords, and they punished them all for their actions, and followed them into the city, where the remaining soldiers also met the same fate as Gargin (13:55). In this way, in 1709, the first tribal national nucleus in Afghanistan was established through the persistent and patriotic efforts of Mirwais Khan and his colleagues, lasting until 1738.

In the 1709 Jirga, the following fighters and celebrities accompanied Mirwais Khan Hotaki: Sayedal Khan Nasir, Babu Jan, Miyaji, Bahadur Khan, Yusuf Khan, Aziz Khan Noorzai, Gul Khan, Noor Khan, Nasru Khan Alokozi, Yahya Khan, Yunus Khan Kakar (6: 151-152).

In general, the Jirga of 1709 can be considered one of the most important and historic assemblies of this era and a clear example of collective political decision-making. In the absence of a regular or formal organization, this Jirga was able to gather influential figures, clergy, and different segments of society to make decisions regarding leadership (choosing Mirwais Khan Hotaki), freedom from oppression and aggression by neighboring powers, and the direction of liberation struggles. Ultimately, these decisions led to the formation of the Hotaki government in Afghanistan.

National Jirga of 1747 (election of Ahmad Shah Abdali as king of Afghanistan)

With the fall of the Hotaki government, the Iranians once again extended their control over Afghanistan, and Nader Afshar captured the cities of Herat, Farah, Kandahar, etc. and became determined to conquer India. Nader Shah Manzoor conquered India and included some Afghan men in his army, including Ahmad Khan, son of Zaman Khan Abdali, a noble and brave young man. The dominance of Nader Afshar and the consolidation of Iranian power for the second time was very unfortunate for the Afghans because the memories of the tyranny and injustice of the “wolf” representative of the Safavid government, had not yet faded. For this reason, the Afghans were trying to eliminate Nader, which ultimately occurred when, after his campaign in India, Nader was killed on his return to Iran in the Khabushan (Quchan) region by his own officers.

The Afshari government led by Nader Afshar collapsed in Afghanistan after nine years, and the Afghan army, composed of Ghuljai, Abdali’s and Uzbeks, went to Kandahar under the command of Noor Mohammad Khan Ghuljai and Ahmad Khan Abdali. They came out to determine the fate of Afghanistan. A Jirga was held in October 1747 in the mansion of Mazar-e-Shir-e-Sarkh inside the Naderabad military fortress and lasted for nine days. However, during these meetings, no consensus was reached on the election of the Shah. Ahmad Khan was not supported by all due to his tribe’s smaller size among the various ethnic groups and tribes of Kandahar. On the ninth day of the Jirga, a sensitive and historic moment occurred: Ahmad Khan was appointed as the king of Afghanistan by Sabir Shah Kabul, a cleric and one of Ahmad Khan’s close associates, who was entrusted by the members of the Jirga to elect a leader for the Afghan tribes (3:19).

The second historic national Jirga in the contemporary history of Afghanistan, held thirty-eight years after the first national Jirga in Kandahar, also led to the formation of a powerful government under the leadership of Ahmad Khan Abdali, who was elected in this Jirga. Ahmad Shah Durrani’s administration significantly increased the size and prestige of Afghanistan and established a vast empire. Having come to power through the votes of the national Jirga, Ahmad Shah secured the support of different tribes and ethnic groups to form a strong and unified kingdom. At the same time, he did not ignore the interests of feudal lords, khans, and other influential figures, both within and outside the Jirga, as well as local leaders.

However, the Abdali (Saduzai) government in Afghanistan, which emerged from the nine-day discussions and negotiations of the historic 1747 National Jirga, lasted from 1747 to 1843, a period of ninety-six years. During this time, the hypocrisy, wars, and struggles of the Saduzai princes over the throne of Afghanistan were also evident (3:20).

In conclusion, the Jirga of Mazar-e-Shir-e-Sorkh holds great importance in the history of Afghanistan. The decisions made in this Jirga resulted in Afghanistan having a powerful ruler and, ultimately, a vast empire over time. In the contemporary history of Afghanistan, the election

of Ahmad Shah Abdali as king by the 1747 Jirga, with the mediation of elders and clerics such as Sabir Shah Kabuli, clearly demonstrates the impact of these Jirgas and their decision-making methods on the future of the country and the consolidation of its position. This event also reflects the prominent role of the aforementioned Jirga as an institution regulating the transfer of power and providing legitimacy to the Afghan political system of that era.

Loya Jirga of 1865 (Consolidation of the system and appointment of the crown prince)

After the death of Amir Dost Mohammad Khan, his son Amir Sher Ali Khan took over the reins of affairs. He, who wanted to consolidate the centralization of the state, spread a new civilization in domestic policy, and ensured the independence of Afghanistan in foreign policy, was a very independent person. He could not remain calm and composed when solving difficult issues. The new Amir of Afghanistan faced a severe internal crisis at the very beginning of his reign because, during the rule of the Mohammadzai brothers, Afghanistan had been governed under a tribal monarchy for more than half a century, and the peasants were under the pressure of exploitation by feudal lords and suffered greatly, which had prepared the ground for internal conflicts as well as ethnic and tribal disputes (8:589).

These conflicts and internal wars were weakening the central government. What attracted the attention of Amir Sher Ali Khan in the first stage was the prevention of conflicts and the assurance of internal security in the country, so that he could implement his reform plans in practice. What could play an effective and active role in the field was the participation of all classes in the affairs of the state. Amir Sher Ali Khan, realizing this and following the ancient national traditions of Afghans, took the initiative to form a Loya Jirga in order to strengthen the political power and position of the monarchy and resolve internal conflicts and problems, seeking a way to address internal problems through the people's vote. Therefore, in 1865, the Great National Jirga was held in Kabul with the participation of two thousand representatives from all classes and tribes of the regions of Afghanistan (9:589).

This great national assembly, which is of national and vital importance in the history of 19th-century Afghanistan, under the chairmanship of the Amir (Sher Ali Khan), in a completely free atmosphere with an understanding of social responsibilities, took beneficial and comprehensive decisions in the field of solving internal problems and conflicts and played its role effectively in resolving internal problems and establishing the monarchy of Amir Sher Ali Khan and his victory over his rivals. Because the decisions of the assembly were communicated by royal decree to the citizens of all Afghanistan, all participants of this historic great assembly, considering the public interests, expressed their cooperation in repelling the Amir's opponents and promoting the welfare of the Afghan people. In this way, Amir Sher Ali Khan was able to overcome internal problems with the cooperation of the representatives of the nation and take a step toward ensuring the internal security of the country.

The Great National and Consultative Jirga of 1865 not only helped Amir Shir Ali Khan against his rival brothers, but they also allowed the Amir to swear allegiance to more than 2,000 people's representatives who had gathered in Kabul, including Turks, Tajiks, Pashtuns, Hazaras, others. He was the grandson of Kahandal Khan of Kandahar and was no more than seven years old when he became the Crown Prince of Afghanistan (4:312).

Shams-ul-Nahar, the official newspaper of the government, which was the only printed newspaper in Afghanistan at the time, recorded the swearing-in ceremony of Prince Abdullah Jan as follows: In 1865, Amir Shir Ali Khan convened a national Jirga in Kabul. Two thousand delegates from all over the world came to Kabul and Marjan Hill was appointed as the venue for

the Crown Prince's celebration. In addition to the representatives of the elected lawyers of the people, hundreds of people gathered at the foot of Marjan Hill to offer Eid prayers, and special military arrangements and magnificent ceremonies were held the sermon was also eloquently delivered from the pulpit to the people (15:29). This sermon contained a lot of information about allegiance and the Crown Prince.

After the end of this sermon, two pieces of collateral, one from the nation's lawyers and the other from Amir Sher Ali Khan himself, were prepared on the occasion of the confirmation and appointment of the crown prince, and were read to the people by Hafiz Qazi Muhammad Amin Khan, who was one of the great scholars.

The mentioned Jirga in the history of Afghanistan shows that Jirgas in Afghanistan have not only played a fundamental role in determining the emperor and forming a new system, but also in stabilizing systems and fostering relations between society and the system. The Jirga of 1865 itself reflects the historical fact that the decisions taken in this Jirga helped to eliminate discord, strengthen solidarity, and ultimately, by electing the Crown Prince, eliminate the grounds for family disputes. This demonstrate the strengthening role of the system and the legitimacy of the transfer of power through the Jirga.

Loya Jirga of 1915 (Declaration of Neutrality in World War I)

At the beginning of his reign, Amir Habibullah Khan did not have a good opinion of British policies in Afghanistan and adopted a method of indifference. All the efforts of the British government during the first years of his reign were unsuccessful until the British representative was able to manipulate Amir Habibullah Khan with intrigue and cunning. The aforementioned Amir signed a contract to strengthen friendship with Britain on March 21, 1905, in Kabul, whereby he assumed all his father's obligations toward the demands of Britain and continued to endanger the independence of Afghanistan. In order to gain further support from the British government, the Amir traveled to India in 1906 with a hundred courtiers, officials, and officers, and three hundred soldiers, at the invitation of the British Indian government. The British political leaders, with all kinds of concessions and promises, captivated the Amir to the point that the Emir did not even mention the immediate independence of Afghanistan during this meeting.

Amir Habibullah Khan's friendly relations with the British Indian government greatly upset the leftist elements of the court who were strongly in favor of the country's independence, because the majority of the leading men of this group, such as Sardar Nasrullah Khan, Sardar Amanullah Khan, Nazer Mohammad Safar Khan, Sardar Abdul Quddus Khan, as well as senior army officers, were in favor of fighting the British and securing the country's independence. The opinion of this group of men was supported by the entire Afghan nation, the borders of the country, as well as intellectuals, clergy, and national merchants, while the rightists of the court were few and favored a policy of compromise with the British(8:738).

But after the Treaty of 1905, Amir Habibullah Khan remained loyal to his friendship with the British until his death and did not even use any favorable opportunity to reject British control of Afghanistan's foreign policy. He declared his neutrality, which aroused the elements opposed to British colonialism, because in every corner of the country there was a general excitement to fight against the British. Under the leadership of Sardar Nasrullah Khan, they expressed their support for war with the British, and the masses of people everywhere talked about war and jihad. However, the delegation returned after almost a year of stay in Afghanistan failed, and Amir Habibullah Khan convened a general Jirga to implement his decisions.

This general assembly was formed in Kabul with 540 representatives, where the social leaders of the jihad against the British had gathered. However, Amir Habibullah Khan, through various tricks and deceptions, was able to keep these leaders occupied in Kabul and secure their support for his neutrality in World War I. The most important members of this assembly were religious scholars who had full spiritual influence in the Afghan society at that time, such as Mullah Najmuddin, Mullah Muhammad Jan, Mullah Abdul Ghafoor, Mullah Muhammad Murid, Hafiz Ji and the sons of Hazrat Mujaddidi Shurbazar, etc. (8:739)

This Jirga convened on Saturday, 1293 AH, in the Salam Khaneh Palace salon at 11:00 AM under the direct chairmanship of Amir Habibullah Khan. In addition to the clergy and representatives of the people, the royal princes, noble commanders, civil and military officials, and courtiers participated.

At the beginning of the session, Amir Habibullah Khan delivered a speech on the political situation in the world, and the events of World War I, and the purpose of forming this Jirga, saying: “Previously, the letter of the Viceroy of India regarding Afghanistan's neutrality in the war and the confirmation of this policy by that government had reached us, and we adopted this neutrality stance. Now we are stating to you again that we will remain steadfast in our neutrality stance under the same conditions as we said, and in this neutrality, we have considered the interests of our government more and have not seen any harm or danger in it. Therefore, the government of Afghanistan is neutral in this current war, does not take sides with any of the belligerent governments, and also does not have the thought of aggression or invasion of the territory of any of the belligerent governments (14:1-2).

After the end of Amir Habibullah Khan's statements on adopting a neutral approach in the World War, which, of course, was more in favor of England, the Shamlin Jirga issued the following resolution: “It is obligatory and necessary for us, honest subjects and the noble Afghan nation, to watch the general war of the European governments with complete calm and tranquility at this time and await its final outcome” (14:4).

Amir Habibullah Khan, using the sacred religious feelings of the people, published a message of obedience to the first authority (the king) with the fatwa of religious scholars and distributed it in all mosques and military fortresses of Afghanistan. British influence in Afghanistan, Iran, and India became increasingly intense, which resulted in the assassination of Amir Habibullah Khan in our country and the complete independence of Afghanistan from the greatest colonial power of the West, Britain.

The 1915 Jirga can be considered another example of political decision-making methods in the history of Afghanistan. The decisions of this Jirga helped manage the Afghan foreign policy crisis of that time and legitimized the regime's decision based on a policy of neutrality, which itself shows that the decisions in these Jirgas were not always uniform. They played different roles in the political life of Afghanistan depending on the time and circumstances.

1922 Jirga (adoption of the 1922 Constitution)

After gaining independence and defeating British imperialism, the Afghan nation entered a new stage of political, economic and social life under the wise guidance of the young Shah, Amir Amanullah Khan. The ideas of democracy, nationalism, Islamic common guarantee, self-determination and socialism had entered the mountainous fortresses of Afghanistan. Sirajul Khabar had spread new ideas in Afghanistan in a nationalist tone and had entered the abstract and intellectual world of Afghanistan (1:181).

Amir Amanullah Khan, without losing any opportunity, initiated administrative reforms, and it was clear that the Amir cherished the desire for the country's greatness and glory. By proposing laws and administrative reforms, he freed the government from the framework of absolutism, which was the legacy of the previous era, and gave it a national character. This government focused most of all on strengthening the foundation of Afghanistan's national unity, and wisely centered this unity on the axis of equality, brotherhood, and equal rights of the Afghan people, and enacted a constitution that is characteristic of national and free systems. In 1301 AH, the first Basic Law of Afghanistan was drafted to ensure public welfare and was approved by the representatives of the nation. This law, which guaranteed the welfare and happiness of the people, clarified the duties and responsibilities of the government towards the nation and the nation towards the government. In order to ratify the articles contained in the aforementioned law and the participation of the nation in their national issues, the lawyers and representatives of the nation were summoned. Since these measures were taken during the winter, summoning all the representatives and lawyers of the nation from all parts of the country would have created obstacles due to the cold weather and transportation problems. Therefore, it was decided that only those representatives of the nation who are members of the State Consultative Assembly and are in Kabul would be sufficient. However, from the eastern side, all the sheikhs of the Sadat, the scholars, and the tribal elders should participate so that they could all advise on the affairs of the country, the progress of the nation, and the articles contained in the constitution that has been prepared in draft form (11:8).

Thus, the Loya Jirga or the Great Consultative Assembly convened in the city of Jalalabad in 1301 AH with the participation of 872 people. The Jirga continued its meetings on the discussion of the draft constitution, which was the core of political life in our society, in a completely free atmosphere and with national interests in mind. They considered it a beneficial step in the social life of our people because this was the first time in the political history of Afghanistan that the government decided to draft a constitution that guaranteed individual and social freedoms and eliminated the gap between the government and the nation. Through this, the Amani government was able to remove the mask of absolutism from its rule by drafting the first constitution and other regulations and establishing consultative assemblies and guiding the people of Afghanistan to the Path of prosperity and progress in the light of the constitution. The Jirga also approved, based on the suggestions of the Shah, that after the Loya Jirga meetings, they would be held every three years in Kabul, the capital of the country, during the summer season, to discuss national issues and government actions.

As a result, the 1922 Jirga is also considered one of the most valuable Jirgas in the contemporary history of Afghanistan. For the first time, traditional Jirgas attempted to form and transition to a formal legal stage and led to the creation of a legal document, the 1922 Constitution. This, in itself, reflects the different role of Jirgas and their decision-making, based on the transition from customs and traditions to new concepts of governance and legal organization.

The history of Jirga in Afghanistan shows that all disputes, large and small, have been resolved very well under this national umbrella. Jirgas play different roles in Afghanistan. History testifies that sometimes Jirga plays the role of a reformer, sometimes the role of a link between the nation and the state, sometimes the authority of legitimacy of systems and sometimes the chapter of the liberation struggles of the Afghan people. Therefore, Jirgas are of special importance in Afghanistan. As we have already mentioned, each chapter of Afghanistan's history has witnessed a national and popular Jirga and it is very difficult to describe all those Jirgas that have occurred continuously in the course of contemporary Afghanistan.

Findings

The findings of this study show that Jirgas in modern Afghan history have not only played a symbolic and consultative role, but but have also played a fundamental and decisive role in the political developments of this country at different stages of modern Afghan history. A study of historical examples of Jirgas shows that the country's major political decisions have been made, in many cases, within the framework of these gatherings and through interaction between socio-political actors.

The first finding of this study shows that in modern Afghan history, political decisions in Jirgas have been based on consensus, consultation, and collective agreement. Unlike centralized power structures, decisions in Jirgas have usually been made through dialogue and seeking the consent of tribal leaders, local elders, and political elites. The use of this method has, in a way, provided legitimacy to the regimes and paved the way for their acceptance in public opinion.

The second point that emerges from this research is that the role and functioning of Jirgas in shaping the system and major political decisions are not fixed and subject to any specific conditions, but have been subject to changes in different periods according to the conditions, demands and objectives in question. In some cases, Jirgas have been a tool for confirming the authority of emerging powers and used as a tool for legitimizing them; while in other cases, they have been used to resolve socio-political conflicts and create a balance between competing powers.

In the third case, the findings of this research seem to be the role of political and social actors in shaping decisions. The composition of Jirgas members, including tribal elders, clergy, local leaders and prominent men, has had a direct impact on the nature of decision-making. The greater presence of each of the parties (representatives of local powers or government representatives) has had a significant impact on ensuring the interests of the parties.

Another finding indicates that political-security opportunities and contexts have played a fundamental role in the way Jirgas operate and make decisions. Political crises, internal and external security threats, serious internal conflicts, and the acquisition of economic and political privileges, especially during periods of power transition, have all had an impact on the way Jirgas make decisions and perform. Finally, the findings show that Jirgas have acted as a bridge between tradition and modernity, in the interaction and adaptation of traditional-social values, modern values, and contemporary governance practices. Undoubtedly, they have sometimes been influential and sometimes influenced in this game, and in traditional societies like Afghanistan, this process continues, and the role of Jirgas remains prominent and influential.

Conclusion

The following research focuses on the period between 1709 and 1922 and shows that Jirgas were among the most important institutions for the formation of powers, the legitimization of systems, and the validation of major national decisions in domestic and foreign affairs. A historical study of Jirgas indicates that, in the modern history of Afghanistan, major political decisions in the national and transnational arena were not only the product of decisions by official institutions, but also sought help from popular Jirgas in the traditional way in gaining legitimacy and validation. Thus, Jirgas functioned beyond a traditional assembly and played a fundamental role as one of the influential elements in the direction of major national decisions and the formation of political systems. The findings of this study reveal that the way political systems are formed and major national decisions are made through Jirgas has not always been uniform, but has sometimes been strongly influenced by the type of system, prevailing

conditions, and socio-political situations. In some cases, Jirgas have been a tool for putting pressure on the government, and in other cases, these Jirgas have been a tool in the hands of state officials to gain legitimacy and implement their programs.

Sometimes, Jirgas were formed and became a tool for putting pressure on on the system, to preserve their traditional and cultural values and to impose their demands on the governments as circumstances required, and in some cases, this confrontation even caused major political developments. Sometimes, Jirgas were formed so that the ruling system, using this great popular platform, could provide the basis for legitimizing and implementing its plans, so as not to be in opposition to the masses of the people.

However, as a result of this research, it becomes clear that these Jirgas have played a fundamental role of mediation between the state and the nation, in the area of matching the values of tradition and modernity, so that the type of leadership from tribalism and the feudal system gradually moves toward the formation of modern, systematic and law-based systems.

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